

A quantitative analysis of the usage of CSID open source/scientific modeling software by popularity, disease coverage, and geography

Karthik Ram, *University of California, Berkeley*

karthik.ram@berkeley.edu

Although the use of research and open-source software has been growing in various research communities over the past decades, it is exceedingly difficult to get a clear picture of what software is used to support research in various domains. One reason for this lack of clarity is that software is hard to cite (technical reasons) unless there is a paper associated with the software itself. Short of publishing a paper for each software (which brings in various new challenges) there are other solutions to overcome these hurdles, such as generating a software bill of materials. However, the use of such tools is uncommon outside of industry software supply chains and security monitoring.

	Technical	Cultural
Software isn't easily citable	✓	✗
Software citations aren't allowed	✗	✓
Software citations aren't indexed	✗	✓
Software isn't peer reviewed	✗	✓
Software can't cite other software	✓	✗

Various barriers to citing software in papers from a [talk](#) delivered at the Free and Open Source Software Developers' European Meeting in February 2020.

Short of novel solutions to documenting software use, the next best solution is to use Named Entity Recognition approaches to uncover software use from structured documents like PDFs. Using Grobid, a machine learning library for extracting, parsing, and re-structuring PDF, into structured XML, along with a training dataset called SoftCite

(<https://github.com/howisonlab/softcite-dataset>), we are now able to extract and disambiguate software mentions from scientific PDFs. When this process is carried out over a corpus of literature, it would be possible to generate a knowledge graph containing information about publications, keywords, authors, institutions, and software and map out mentions over time. It also opens up the possibility of asking research questions about the data such as:

1. What collections of software are driving research in a particular domain?
2. How have the types of software used changed over time?
3. Are there opportunities for collaboration and intervention (e.g. such as supporting weak links in the software ecosystem)?
4. Are there opportunities for new tools to reduce friction in the flow of information through the ecosystem?

Thus far, we have processed over 2 million open-access articles from the [unpaywall corpus](#). One limitation of this dataset is that it primarily focuses on literature from biomedical research and economics, so it is not representative of the core literature in CSID. While we can repeat this process with a DOI list or collection of papers, for now, our knowledge graph does not contain exhaustive mentions of software used in this community.

Approach

I searched all of the terms listed in Appendix A Key Search Terms of the [Landscape mapping of software tools for climate-sensitive infectious disease modelling](#) report by Inter-American Institute for Global Change Research: IAI. Keeping in mind that this is not exclusively CSID literature or even exhaustive (like PubMed), the results were interesting nevertheless.

In terms of programming languages used in papers that matched the search criteria, I found a total of 897 languages and frameworks that were used. A tally is available [here](#).

The top 10 languages were:

Software	total
----------	-------

R	310
C++	176
C	148
Java	83
Python	63
JavaScript	31
Fortran	31
assembly language	16
Objective-C	5

In terms of scientific software, I uncovered 2038 unique software¹ tools that were used to carry out the research. A full list is available [here](#). Although Grobid typically excludes modeling frameworks, many still appear on the list. With some additional work, one could map out the software ecosystems for each disease or CSID area by traversing dependency graphs. With greater awareness of software ecosystems driving research in specific CSID areas, one could support COPs through training, software development, funding gaps in the infrastructure, etc.

Discussion

This preliminary analysis of a swath of scientific literature from biomedical research covering CSID-related search terms provides some interesting insights. There were ~2038 unique pieces of software used in ~4,801 papers. Many of these tools form the foundation of operationalized models that are being used to cure various diseases. Gaining a deeper understanding of this ecosystem can be used to fill in gaps observed outside of vector-borne diseases (Inter-American Institute for Global Change Research: IAI 2022), develop training programs to support the next generation of modelers, and direct funding toward the weakest nodes of the software ecosystem.

¹ The dataset has not been perfectly deduplicated (e.g. there are mentions of R package randomforest and randomforest) but the ballpark number of tools will not change dramatically.

Literature Cited

Inter-American Institute for Global Change Research: IAI. 2022. "Landscape Mapping of Software Tools for Climate-Sensitive Infectious Disease Modelling." Wellcome. 2022. <https://wellcome.org/reports/landscape-mapping-software-tools-climate-sensitive-infectious-disease-modelling>.